

Accession Number: P425007

17 mag 2017

Patient ID: P27515

Optima CT660

Exam Description: TERMO-ABLAZIONE TC GUI

Report Dose

Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
1	Scout	-	-	-	-
2	Helical	I147.750-I194.000	6.16	129.72	Body 32
3	Helical	I144.000-I176.500	6.23	60.32	Body 32
4	Helical	I145.000-I176.250	6.25	59.74	Body 32
5	Helical	I145.000-I160.000	5.66	44.91	Body 32
6	Helical	I145.000-I160.000	5.54	43.93	Body 32
7	Helical	I145.000-I160.000	5.78	45.89	Body 32
8	Helical	I145.000-I160.000	5.52	43.81	Body 32
9	Helical	I145.000-I160.000	5.93	47.08	Body 32
Total Exam DLP:				475.40	